

Maxwell's Demon and Irreversible Ideal Gas Expansion?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 10, 2025

In (1), a single particle (which represents an ideal gas) is present in a container of volume V coupled presumably to a reservoir at temperature T . A Maxwell demon knows the position of the particle and inserts a partition in the middle of the container when the particle is near the left hand wall. The particle then isothermally pushes the partition to the right hand wall and the system is back to its initial state (claim). Heat from the reservoir has been converted entirely into work violating the second law of thermodynamics.

Here we argue that placing a partition at $V/2$ when the original state was V already violates the second law of thermodynamics because the entropy changes from $C_1 \ln(V)$ to $C_1 \ln(V/2)$, i.e. the system becomes more ordered with no effort. In a previous note (2), we have made a similar argument, namely that if the particle, representing an ideal gas, was originally in V and is now in $V/2$, then work must have been done to push it into $V/2$ isothermally. Then there is no issue with it expanding back to its original state (see (2)).

Here we argue that the instant the demon places a participation at $V/2$, the starting volume is $V/2$ and the spatial entropy $\ln(V/2)$. We suggest that in order to not violate the second law of entropy, one may treat this problem as having an initial state of $V/2$ and analyzing from that point on because the sudden change from V to $V/2$ is not consistent with the second law.

Thus, heat from the reservoir matches the isothermal work, but there is an increase in entropy as the particle (or gas) moves from $V/2$ to V . In such a case there is no violation of the second law of thermodynamics. We argue that this is the quasistatic path equivalent to an irreversible expansion of an ideal gas. The overall effect is an increase in entropy in the gas which does not violate the second law of thermodynamics

Maxwell Demon Argument

In (1), a Maxwell demon argument is presented as following. A demon exists who knows the position of particles. An ideal gas consisting of a single particle sits in a box of volume V . The demon who knows the position of the particle places a partition in the center of the box when the particle is near the left hand wall. The particle then isothermally pushes the partition to the right hand wall, presumably restoring the initial state. It seems that there must be a heat reservoir at temperature T if isothermal work is done. Thus, heat from the reservoir is converted entirely into work with no other consequences hence violating the second law of thermodynamics. (1) then goes on to analyze the situation using a Szilard map. We try to argue that the particle does not return to its initial state (volume V) because when the partition is added, one has a particle in a box of size $V/2$ and this is the initial state. Later it expands to size meaning that there is an increase in entropy. (To have the particle jump form V to $V/2$ means an entropy decrease with no effort and this violates the second law.)

Real Initial State

A single particle representing an ideal gas is in a box of volume V . This means it is associated with a spatial entropy of $\ln(V)$. If a partition is placed at $V/2$ when the particle is at the right hand side of the box, the initial state is now one of spatial entropy $\ln(V/2)$ and not $\ln(V)$ and we argue that this changes the whole problem. In such a case, an amount of Q from the reservoir enters in to compensate for the isothermal work done by the single particle gas on the partition. At the same time, the entropy of the single particle increases from $\ln(V/2)$ to $\ln(V)$. Thus, an entropy loss from the reservoir of $-Q/T$ results in an entropy increase in the single particle gas and work done by the single particle gas of magnitude Q . Heat from the reservoir is not converted entirely into work, an entropy increase in the gas also occurs and so the second law of thermodynamics is not violated.

From (1): isothermal work = $-nRT \int_{(V/2, V)} dV/V = nRT \ln(2)$ ((1))

Thus: $Q = nRT \ln(2)$ and $-Q/T = nR \ln(2) = k \ln(2)$ ((2))

From the Sackur-Tetrode equation for ideal gas entropy, a change in entropy from $V/2$ to V with T and N remaining constant is:

ΔS (gas or single particle gas) = $kN \{ \ln(V) - \ln(V/2) \}$ ((3))

For $N=1$, one has: $\Delta S = k \ln(2)$ Using $nR = Nk = k$ for $N=1$

For the universe, the heat reservoir loses entropy $-k \ln(2)$, but the gas (single particle) gains the same amount of entropy so the overall entropy change of the universe is 0.

It seems that there is no violation of the second law of thermodynamics if one considers the starting volume as $V/2$.

We further argue that this problem is similar to that of an irreversible expansion of an ideal gas from $V/2$ to V . In such a case, T is constant so E is constant and no work is done. For a single particle gas, the change in entropy is ((3)), i.e. $k \ln(2)$. One may obtain this value using a reversible process (i.e. isothermal) meaning that entropy of the universe remains constant and so knowing work from ((1)), one may find Q and hence the change in the entropy of the gas, which is the goal of considering the reversible process because even though the reversible path is not the same as the irreversible one, the starting and ending entropy state points are the same.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that having a single particle (ideal gas) in a container of volume V and having a demon place a partition at $V/2$ when the particle is near the left hand wall already violates the second law of thermodynamics because entropy decreases with no work being

done (and no energy change as well). In a previous note, we argued that if the particle is to the left of the center of the box, then isothermal work was done to push it there from a volume of V , with a heat term as well, and this counterbalances the heat from a reservoir and the work done by the single particle gas when it expands back to V . Here, we give an alternative view. We suggest that the second law is violated when a partition is placed at $V/2$ with the single particle (representing an entire gas) is to the left of the center. We suggest that one must take $V/2$ as the starting point. Then, the reservoir supplies heat and it is converted to work, but the entropy of the single particle gas also increases and the second law is not violated, we argue.

References

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